

To publish or to republish, that is the question: is the right of republication just palliative care?

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Abstract

Why do so many European countries grant scientific authors who receive public funding a right of republication (or secondary publication) that allows them to make their work freely available to the public even if they have assigned their copyright to a commercial publisher?

If scholars really want to make a public use of reason in the Kantian sense, why is publication not enough?

The root of such a predicament is not copyright, which can be circumvented to foster a growing public domain instead of commercial monopolies, as the GNU-GPL and Creative Commons licenses show. It is an evaluation of research that has been separated from the discussion among researchers who can understand and critique the "content" of the papers, to be placed in the hands of bureaucrats, or scholars working as bureaucrats, who use bibliometrics to make calculations about "containers" or publication venues.

As a result, the owners of the containers, which have become indispensable for evaluating research and deciding on researchers' careers, have been able to impose restrictive copyright terms on authors and their institutions and to extract ever higher prices from a kind of publishing that no longer has anything to do with "making public". In countries like Italy, whose legislation does not even recognize the right of republication, their oligopolistic position is even stronger because bibliometric evaluation is not only centralized, but also mandated by a government-appointed agency, ANVUR.

Therefore, a right of secondary publication could certainly help – and in Italy more than elsewhere – , but just as a palliative to a crisis of publication that could only be overcome by burning its root, which is a journal-based evaluation of research.

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1 The secondary publication paradox

The right of re-publication or right of secondary publication allows scientific authors who receive public funding to make their work freely available to the public, even if they have signed away their copyright in a contract with a commercial publisher.¹

Although it is recognized in all central-western European countries except Italy,² it contains a paradox: why do scientific authors working in universities and public research institutions need a special right to *republish* texts already *published* by commercial publishers? What is the function of the first “publication” if, despite its name, it is not to make texts available to the public?

In the last decade of the last century it was already possible to make public use of reason, circumventing the mediation of publishers who “publish” without making texts public.³ In 1989, Tim Berners-Lee invented the World Wide Web so that “any person could share information with anyone else, anywhere”.⁴ In 1991, when CERN offered it to the world, the interest of a part of the scientific community in sharing their research led to the first open disciplinary repository, the ArXiv, now hosted by Cornell University and funded by universities and other research institutions. The GNU-GPL license also dates back to 1989. And at the turn of the millennium, it was joined by the GNU Free Documentation License and the Creative Commons by and by-sa licenses to help make not only the source code of software, but all works of authorship publicly available.

More than thirty years later,⁵ ArXiv’s access control remains minimalist: personal knowledge (endorsement) is supplemented by “light” moderation, assisted by a machine learning program that selects papers requiring moderator intervention. Moderation does not guarantee scholarly quality, but it does ensure that texts are usable and identifiable, and it filters out papers that are off-topic or do not meet academic standards. And yet, as Paul Ginsparg notes,⁶ during the pandemic, open repositories helped to quickly discard poorly-founded hypotheses and introduce new recommendations and effective treatments,⁷ while some of

¹Roberto Caso and Giulia Dore. “Academic Copyright, Open Access and the “Moral” Second Publication Right”. In: *European Intellectual Property Review* (2021). doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5764841. url: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5764841>.

² Knowledge Rights 21. *A Position Statement from Knowledge Rights 21 on Secondary Publishing Rights*. 2023. url: url, In 2019, an attempt to overcome Law No. 112 of 7 October 2013, which disregarded EU recommendations on embargoed open access, by introducing a moderate secondary publication right, was blocked in the Italian Senate after being approved in the Chamber of Deputies: Roberto Caso, *La proposta di legge Gallo sull'accesso aperto all'informazione scientifica (DDL n. 1146)*, 2019 <https://aisa.sp.unipi.it/sulla-proposta-di-legge-gallo-sullaccesso-aperto-allinformazione-scientifica-ddl-n-1146>.

³In the age of the printing press, copyright could be justified as an industrial regulation to protect authors from publishers, rather than to protect publishers and other kinds of distributors from the public and from authors themselves, if they are interested in making public use of reason (Richard Stallman. *Freedom or Copyright? - GNU Project - Free Software Foundation*. 2008. url: <https://www.gnu.org/philosophy/freedom-or-copyright.html>).

⁴Tim Berners-Lee. “Long Live the Web: A Call for Continued Open Standards and Neutrality”. In: *Scientific American* (2010). url: http://www.scientificamerican.com/article.cfm?id=long-live-the-web,%20https://www.cs.virginia.edu/~robins/Long_Live_the_Web.pdf.

⁵Paul Ginsparg. “Lessons from arXiv’s 30 Years of Information Sharing”. In: *Nature Reviews Physics* 3.9 (2021), pp. 602–603. issn: 2522-5820. doi: 10.1038/s42254-021-00360-z.

⁶Ibid.

⁷K. Randall et al. “How Did We Get Here: What Are Droplets and Aerosols and How Far Do They Go? A Historical Perspective on the Transmission of Respiratory Infectious Diseases”. In: *Interface Focus* 11.6 (2021), p. 20210049. doi: 10.1098/rsfs.2021.0049 was originally shared on SSRN;

Elsevier's closed peer-reviewed journals published articles on questionable remedies such as hydroxychloroquine⁸ and ivermectin.⁹ And even before the pandemic, Jean-Claude Guédon wondered whether scientific journals themselves, structured around the economic and technical constraints of the press, should be overtaken by a development model inspired by free software. All we need to do is to identify authors – for example with ORCID – and texts – for example with DOI – and find ways to discuss and select them with a kind of public peer review. Do we really need journals that mimic print to do that?

It may be a surprise to discover that the very notion of journal may act as a form of blockage, but this is the case if the journal is taken as a proxy of the Great Conversation. The same would have been true, at the end of the Middle Ages, if *scriptoria* had been taken as a proxy of the copy-function.¹⁰

2 Secondary publication right: just palliative care?

Fraud¹¹ to make papers spicy enough to be published in highly cited commercial journals, tricks to artificially multiply citations,¹² and the inflation of scientific literature under the "publish or perish" imperative¹³ cannot be dismissed as "anecdotal"

Peter Horby et al. *Effect of Dexamethasone in Hospitalized Patients with COVID-19 – Preliminary Report*. 2020. doi: 10.1101/2020.06.22.20137273. URL: <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.06.22.20137273v1>.

⁸Philippe Gautret et al. "Hydroxychloroquine and Azithromycin as a Treatment of COVID-19: Results of an Open-Label Non-Randomized Clinical Trial". In: *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents* 56.1 (2020), p. 105949. ISSN: 0924-8579. doi: 10.1016/j.ijantimicag.2020.105949. The article was not retracted, although a letter of concern from the journal's publishing society, the International Society of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy, had publicly criticized it. (Adam Marcus. *Hydroxychloroquine-COVID-19 Study Did Not Meet Publishing Society's "Expected Standard"*. 2020. URL: <https://retractionwatch.com/2020/04/06/hydroxychlorine-covid-19-study-did-not-meet-publishing-societys-expected-standar>). Later, it became clear that the article was just the tip of an iceberg (Kathleen O'Grady. "The Reckoning. Didier Raoult and His Institute Found Fame during the Pandemic. Then, a Group of Dogged Critics Exposed Major Ethical Failings". In: *Science* 383.6687 (2024). URL: <https://www.science.org/content/article/failure-every-level-how-science-sleuths-exposed-massive-ethics-violations-famed-french>).

⁹Leon Caly et al. "The FDA-approved Drug Ivermectin Inhibits the Replication of SARS-CoV-2 in Vitro". In: *Antiviral Research* 178 (2020), p. 104787. ISSN: 0166-3542. doi: 10.1016/j.antiviral.2020.104787.

¹⁰Niels Stern, Jean-Claude Guédon, and Thomas Wiben Jensen. "Crystals of Knowledge Production. An Intercontinental Conversation about Open Science and the Humanities". In: *Nordic Perspectives on Open Science* 1 (2015). doi: 10.7557/11.3619.

¹¹See, just for instance John P. A. Ioannidis. "Why most published research findings are false". In: *PLoS Medicine* 2 (2005). doi: 10.1371/journal.pmed.0020124. URL: <http://journals.plos.org/plosmedicine/article?id=10.1371/journal.pmed.0020124>, Jerome R. Ravetz. "How Should We Treat Sciences Growing Pains?" In: *the Guardian* (2016). URL: <http://www.theguardian.com/science/political-science/2016/jun/08/how-should-we-treat-sciences-growing-pains>

¹²Alberto Baccini, Giuseppe De Nicolao, and Eugenio Petrovich. "Citation Gaming Induced by Bibliometric Evaluation: A Country-Level Comparative Analysis". In: *PLOS ONE* 14.9 (2019). ISSN: 1932-6203. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0221212.

¹³See for instance Mark A. Edwards and Siddharta Roy. "Academic Research in the 21st Century: Maintaining Scientific Integrity in a Climate of Perverse Incentives and Hypercompetition". In: *Environmental engineering science* (2016). doi: 10.1089/ees.2016.0223. URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5206685/>; Richard Van Noorden. "How Big Is Science's Fake-Paper Problem?" In: *Nature* 623.7987 (2023). doi: 10.1038/d41586-023-03464-x, Eiko Fried. *Antidotes to Cynicism Creep in Academia*. 2024. URL: <https://eiko-fried.com/antidotes-to-cynicism-creep>.

– and not just because scientific theories are not mass-produced items whose quality can be determined by weapons of mass evaluation.¹⁴ The dysfunctionality,¹⁵ cost and unreliability of commercial scientific publishing are now being denounced not only by open science advocates such as Björn Brembs,¹⁶ but also by the mainstream press itself¹⁷ and the Council of the European Union, which recommends that publishing be returned to the hands of the scientific community.¹⁸

What happened to *publication* if it has become crucial to grant scholars a new right of *republishing* so that they can make a public use of reason?

The answer is well known¹⁹ and now widely shared in European institutions:²⁰ an evaluation of research that is no longer part of the discussion among researchers who understand and critique "content," but has been given away in the hands of bureaucrats, or scholars working as bureaucrats,²¹ who make calculations about "containers" or publication venues. As a result, the owners of the containers that have become essential to the evaluation of research and the careers of researchers have been able to impose restrictive copyright terms on authors and their institutions, and to extract ever higher prices for either reading²² or publishing,²³ or reading and publishing²⁴ – while researchers are under pressure to *publish* at all

¹⁴As the Wakefield case has shown, even a single paper can cause very serious social and public health damage: Julia Belluz. *20 Years Ago, Research Fraud Catalyzed the Anti-Vaccination Movement. Lets Not Repeat History*. 2018. URL: <https://www.vox.com/2018/2/27/17057990/andrew-wakefield-vaccines-autism-study>.

¹⁵Claudio Aspesi. *The time has come: L'ecosistema editoriale accademico dopo il COVID-19 [OWeek2021]*. Version 1. Oct. 2021. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5599575.

¹⁶Björn Brembs. *The Trinity of Failures*. 2021. URL: <https://bjoern.brembs.net/2021/10/trinity-of-failures/>.

¹⁷Robin McKie. "The Situation Has Become Appalling: Fake Scientific Papers Push Research Credibility to Crisis Point". In: *The Guardian* (2024). URL: <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2024/feb/03/the-situation-has-become-appalling-fake-scientific-papers-push-research-credibility-to-crisis-point>.

¹⁸Competitiveness Council conclusions, *Council conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing*, May 2023: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-8827-2023-INIT/en/pdf>; *Joint statement: Council conclusions on not-for-profit scholarly communication ecosystem*, 2023 <https://www.scienceeurope.org/our-resources/joint-statement-council-conclusions-on-not-for-profit-scholarly-communication-ecosystem/> : "As key public research and innovation actors in Europe, we are committed to supporting the development of a publicly owned, not-for-profit scholarly communication ecosystem in collaboration with policymakers in Europe and beyond."

¹⁹Jean-Claude Guédon. *In Oldenburgs Long Shadow. Librarians, Research Scientists, Publishers, and the Control of Scientific Publishing*. Washington D.C.: Association of Research Libraries, 2001. URL: <https://www.arl.org/wp-content/uploads/2001/12/in-oldenburgs-long-shadow.pdf>.

²⁰Francesca Di Donato. "What we talk about when we talk about research quality". In: *Bollettino telematico di filosofia politica* (2024). URL: <https://commentbfp.sp.unipi.it/quality-fdd/ġ1>.

²¹Mario Biagioli. "Quality to Impact, Text to Metadata: Publication and Evaluation in the Age of Metrics". In: *KNOW: A Journal on the Formation of Knowledge 2.2* (2018), pp. 249–275. URL: <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/10.1086/699152>.

²²Stephen Buranyi. "Is the Staggeringly Profitable Business of Scientific Publishing Bad for Science?" In: *the Guardian* (2017). URL: <http://www.theguardian.com/science/2017/jun/27/profitable-business-scientific-publishing-bad-for-science>.

²³Juan Pablo Alperin. "Why I Think Ending Article-Processing Charges Will Save Open Access". In: *Nature* 610.7931 (2022), pp. 233–233.

²⁴Jon Tennant. "'Transformative' Open Access Publishing Deals Are Only Entrenching Commercial Power". In: *Times Higher Education (THE)* (2019); Leigh-Ann Butler et al. "The Oligopolys Shift to Open Access Publishing: How for-Profit Publishers Benefit from Gold and Hybrid Article Processing Charges". In: *Proceedings of the Annual Conference of CAIS | Actes Du Congrès Annuel de IACSI*. 2022. doi: 10.29173/cais1262; Maria Chiara Pievatolo, *Contratti trasformativi: perché, in Italia, varrebbe la pena discuterne*, AISA, 2024 <https://aisa.sp.unipi.it/contratti->

costs, or perish.

In Italy, the evaluation of research is not only performed by administrators, but is also centralized in an agency, ANVUR, whose board of directors is appointed by the government.²⁵ For the humanities and social sciences, the agency determines which journals are scientific and which are not, and which scientific journals are excellent and which are not, on the basis of lists drawn up by scientists under its control; for mathematics, physics and the natural sciences, it relies on the proprietary databases Scopus and Clarivate Analytics, in the hands of commercial private oligopolies. ANVUR uses its governmental and corporate bibliometrics to set mandatory quantitative thresholds, both for researchers applying for the National Scientific Qualification for Professorship (ASN) and for the commissioners who will evaluate them.²⁶ Of course, the publishers of journals listed by ANVUR or by Scopus and Clarivate Analytics are also blessed with the privilege of *publishing without making public*.

In this context, the introduction of a right of republication in Italy would certainly be an important step. However, it would remain exposed to the risk of being only a palliative for the disease of publishers who do not honor their name – unless Italian scholars regain the independence or the interest to challenge the dystopian alliance of big government (state evaluation) and big business (private intellectual monopolies) that has kidnapped the publication and continues to hold it captive.

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²⁵Maria Chiara Pievatolo. "The Scale and the Sword: Science, State and Research Evaluation". In: *Bollettino telematico di filosofia politica* (2024). URL: <https://commentbfp.sp.unipi.it/maria-chiara-pievatolo-the-scale-and-the-sword-statal-science-and-research-evaluation>.

²⁶M.C. Pievatolo, Taking all the running one can do, to keep in the same place: ANVURs complicated relationship with the COARA agreement, 2023-24.